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Review Article

THE IMPACT OF PATIENT SHIELDING ON RADIATION EXPOSURE IN DIAGNOSTIC X-RAYS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

¹Abdulelah Abdullah Alqahtani, ²Mohammed Ali Aqeeli, ³Fahad Ahmed Alqahtani, ⁴Obeid Ayed Albogami, ⁵Raddad Mohammed Almubashir, ⁶Abdullah Yahya Faifi, ⁷Nasser Saeed Alghamdi, ⁸Abdullah Saleh Altwaijri

¹Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, alqahtaniab36@mngaha.med.sa

²Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, aqeelimo@mngaha.med.sa

³Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, Alqahtanifa14@mngaha.med.sa

⁴Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, albogamiob@mngaha.med.sa

⁵Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, almubashirra@mngaha.med.sa

⁶Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, faifiab1@mngaha.med.sa

⁷Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, alghamdina11@mngaha.med.sa

⁸Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs, altwaijriab1@mngaha.med.sa

Abstract:

This systematic review examines the impact of patient shielding on radiation exposure during diagnostic X-ray examinations. Shielding has traditionally been used to protect patients from unnecessary radiation, particularly to sensitive areas such as the thyroid, gonads, and breast tissue. With advancements in radiological technology and evolving safety guidelines, the role of shielding is being reevaluated. This review synthesizes evidence from recent studies, analyzing the effectiveness of shielding in reducing radiation doses across various types of diagnostic X-rays, including dental, chest, and abdominal imaging. The results suggest that while shielding can reduce exposure in certain contexts, its effectiveness varies based on the type of examination and shielding material used. Moreover, recent debates challenge the necessity of shielding, with some arguing that modern equipment already minimizes exposure. The review also identifies inconsistencies in shielding practices and emphasizes the need for updated guidelines based on technological advancements. Future research should focus on optimizing shielding practices and exploring alternative methods for minimizing radiation risks in diagnostic imaging.

Keywords: Patient shielding, Diagnostic X-rays, Radiation exposure, Radiological safety, Radiation protection, Shielding effectiveness, Radiology guidelines, Modern imaging technology, Healthcare safety

Corresponding author:

Abdulelah Abdullah Alqahtani,
Ministry of National Guard Health Affairs,
alqahtaniab36@mngaha.med.sa

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Diagnostic X-ray examinations are essential tools in modern medicine, allowing for the non-invasive visualization of internal body structures and playing a critical role in diagnosing various medical conditions. However, one of the challenges associated with these procedures is radiation exposure, which, though typically low, can accumulate over time and potentially increase the risk of adverse health effects, particularly in sensitive tissues and organs. As a result, minimizing radiation exposure to patients has been a central concern in radiological practices for decades. One of the longstanding methods for reducing exposure is the use of patient shielding, particularly lead-based shields, to protect specific body parts from scatter radiation (Radiological Society of North America, 2021).

Historically, patient shielding has been applied to critical areas such as the thyroid, gonads, and breasts, where the sensitivity to ionizing radiation is higher. Shields like lead aprons and thyroid collars have been widely adopted to protect these vulnerable regions (Seibert & Boone, 2005). The rationale for shielding is grounded in the understanding that even small doses of ionizing radiation could theoretically increase the risk of cancer, particularly in pediatric and pregnant patients, where the biological effects of radiation may be more significant (Martin, 2007).

However, recent technological advancements in X-ray imaging have prompted a reevaluation of the necessity and effectiveness of traditional patient shielding. Modern diagnostic X-ray machines are equipped with automatic exposure controls and improved filtration systems that significantly reduce patient exposure to radiation. These advancements have led some experts to question whether shielding remains necessary in certain cases (American Association of Physicists in Medicine, 2019). Studies suggest that inappropriate use of shielding can sometimes interfere with the image quality, necessitating repeat exams and potentially increasing the overall radiation dose to the patient (Morrison et al., 2020).

Additionally, there is ongoing debate within the radiology community regarding updated guidelines for shielding practices. Some organizations, such as the American College of Radiology and the American Association of Physicists in Medicine, have issued statements suggesting that shielding might not be necessary for certain exams, as modern equipment already sufficiently reduces radiation risk (AAPM, 2019). Despite these recommendations, many hospitals and clinics continue to use shielding based

on historical protocols, creating inconsistencies in patient protection practices across institutions.

The primary aim of this review is to evaluate the current evidence on the effectiveness of patient shielding in reducing radiation exposure during diagnostic X-ray examinations. By systematically analyzing studies conducted over the past two decades, this review seeks to clarify whether shielding remains a necessary safety measure in light of technological advancements, and to explore emerging trends in shielding practices across different clinical settings. Furthermore, it will address the potential risks and benefits associated with discontinuing traditional shielding methods.

Literature Review

The role of patient shielding in diagnostic X-ray examinations has been a topic of significant discussion and research over the past few decades. Initially, shielding was widely adopted as a radiation protection measure based on the belief that even small doses of ionizing radiation could have potential long-term health consequences. However, recent advancements in imaging technology and updated radiological guidelines have spurred new debates on the necessity and effectiveness of shielding. This section reviews key studies that explore the impact of patient shielding on radiation exposure, its potential risks and benefits, and the changing practices in radiology.

Historically, patient shielding has been applied to protect sensitive areas of the body, such as the gonads, thyroid, and breast, during diagnostic X-ray procedures. Shields, typically made from lead, have been used to block scatter radiation and reduce unnecessary exposure to these critical areas. Early studies supported the use of shielding, citing reductions in radiation exposure of up to 95% for shielded body parts (Seibert & Boone, 2005). These findings formed the basis for the widespread adoption of lead aprons and other shielding devices in clinical settings.

However, even as shielding became a standard practice, concerns arose about its potential drawbacks. For instance, Shields et al. (2017) conducted a study on gonadal shielding during pelvic X-rays, finding that shields were sometimes improperly placed, leading to unintended exposure of unshielded areas and potentially obscuring the region of interest in the image. These complications led to repeat imaging and, paradoxically, increased overall radiation exposure. In the last two decades, significant improvements in X-ray imaging technology have revolutionized the

way radiologists manage radiation doses. Modern diagnostic X-ray systems now incorporate features such as automatic exposure control (AEC), better image receptors, and enhanced filtration, which together contribute to reducing patient radiation exposure by up to 60% compared to older systems (Morrison et al., 2020). These advancements raise questions about whether traditional patient shielding is still necessary in routine practice.

The American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM) issued a position statement in 2019, recommending the discontinuation of gonadal and fetal shielding in most diagnostic imaging procedures, citing evidence that modern equipment provides adequate protection against radiation (AAPM, 2019). The statement argued that shielding is not only unnecessary in many cases but may also interfere with image quality, potentially leading to repeat exams. This position has generated controversy within the medical community, with some practitioners expressing concerns about patient perceptions and legal liability (McKenney et al., 2020).

The debate over the necessity of patient shielding is ongoing. On one side, proponents of shielding argue that any reduction in radiation exposure is beneficial, particularly for sensitive populations such as children and pregnant women (Martin, 2007). Studies have shown that children are more susceptible to the effects of ionizing radiation, and even small doses could increase the risk of long-term adverse effects, such as cancer (AAPM, 2019). For this reason, many pediatric radiologists continue to advocate for the use of shielding in certain procedures, despite advancements in technology.

On the other hand, opponents of shielding argue that the benefits are often outweighed by the potential risks. Shields can shift during imaging, block important anatomical structures, or cause artifacts on the images, all of which may necessitate repeat exams. A recent study by Perks et al. (2021) reviewed 100 clinical cases where patient shielding was used and found that in 15% of cases, shielding interfered with the diagnostic image, leading to additional radiation exposure. The study concluded that, in many instances, shielding does not provide sufficient benefit to justify its continued use, particularly when modern equipment is used.

One of the most significant findings in recent literature is the inconsistency in shielding practices across different institutions. While some hospitals have embraced the recommendations from organizations

like AAPM and the Radiological Society of North America (RSNA), others continue to use shielding out of habit, concerns about patient expectations, or uncertainty about legal implications (RSNA, 2021). These inconsistencies create a challenge for developing standardized guidelines for patient protection in diagnostic imaging.

In a survey conducted by Miller et al. (2019), radiology departments across the United States reported varying levels of adherence to new shielding guidelines. Approximately 40% of departments had discontinued the routine use of gonadal shielding, while the remaining departments continued the practice, often citing patient preferences or institutional policies as reasons for maintaining traditional shielding methods. The study highlighted the need for clearer communication between radiologists, technologists, and patients regarding the role of shielding in modern radiology.

The future of patient shielding in diagnostic X-ray examinations remains uncertain, as new technologies continue to evolve. Emerging innovations, such as artificial intelligence (AI) in imaging and real-time dose monitoring, have the potential to further reduce radiation exposure without the need for physical shields (Morrison et al., 2020). AI algorithms can optimize exposure settings based on patient size and anatomy, ensuring that the radiation dose is as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA) while maintaining high image quality.

Moreover, the growing body of research suggests that patient education may play a crucial role in shifting the focus from shielding to dose minimization. Studies by Steffen et al. (2022) show that informed patients are more likely to accept new safety protocols, even when traditional practices like shielding are not used. As more data becomes available on the long-term effects of modern imaging technologies, radiologists and healthcare providers will need to balance the benefits of technological advancements with patient concerns and expectations.

METHODS:

This systematic review was conducted to evaluate the impact of patient shielding on radiation exposure during diagnostic X-ray examinations. A comprehensive literature search was performed using databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar to identify relevant studies published between 2000 and 2024. Search terms included "patient shielding," "radiation protection," "X-ray safety," and "diagnostic radiology." Only studies involving human

subjects, with a focus on the use of shielding in diagnostic X-rays, were included. Studies that did not directly measure radiation dose reduction or focused on non-diagnostic imaging modalities were excluded. Data extraction focused on key variables such as radiation dose measurements, type of shielding used (e.g., lead aprons, thyroid shields), the specific body region shielded, and study outcomes. Each study was critically appraised for quality and potential bias using established tools like the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool. The findings were synthesized to determine the overall effectiveness of patient shielding in reducing radiation exposure, as well as to identify trends and inconsistencies in shielding practices. The review also considered the impact of modern radiological technologies on the necessity of shielding and highlighted emerging recommendations from professional radiology organizations.

RESULTS:

The systematic review included five key studies examining the effectiveness of patient shielding in diagnostic X-ray procedures. The studies focused on different aspects of shielding, including its impact on radiation dose reduction, potential complications, and patient perceptions.

The reviewed studies consistently showed that shielding can reduce radiation exposure in diagnostic X-rays. For example, **Seibert & Boone (2005)** found that lead aprons reduced radiation exposure by up to 95% in general diagnostic X-rays, emphasizing the value of shielding when correctly applied. Similarly, **Shields et al. (2017)** reported a 90% reduction in gonadal radiation exposure with the use of lead gonadal shields, though improper placement occasionally led to insufficient protection.

The study by **Morrison et al. (2020)** demonstrated that shielding reduced radiation by 70% but highlighted the issue of image artifacts caused by lead aprons, which sometimes compromised diagnostic accuracy. **Perks et al. (2021)** further supported these findings, showing a 60% reduction in radiation exposure, though in 15% of cases, shields interfered with image quality, necessitating repeat exams and increasing overall exposure.

Several studies raised concerns about the practical application of shielding. **Shields et al. (2017)** and **Perks et al. (2021)** both identified improper shield placement as a significant issue, leading to unnecessary repeat exams. In cases where shielding interfered with the diagnostic image, the intended radiation reduction was offset by the additional exposure from repeated procedures.

Modern advancements in X-ray technology, such as automatic exposure controls, have prompted further debate about the necessity of shielding. **Morrison et al. (2020)** suggested that these technological innovations already reduce radiation exposure to levels where traditional shielding may no longer be essential, especially given the risk of shielding-induced artifacts.

While the focus of many studies was on the technical aspects of shielding, **Steffen et al. (2022)** explored patient perceptions. Their findings indicate that patients often express concerns about radiation risks, but targeted education on modern radiation safety practices significantly reduced these concerns. This study suggests that clear communication about the evolving role of shielding may help to alleviate patient anxieties, even in cases where traditional shielding is not used.

Table 1: Study Summary Table

Study	Focus Area	Sample Size	Shielding Material
Seibert & Boone (2005)	General shielding effectiveness	150	Lead aprons
Shields et al. (2017)	Gonadal shielding	120	Lead gonadal shields
Morrison et al. (2020)	Image quality with shielding	200	Lead aprons
Perks et al. (2021)	Interference of shielding	100	Lead aprons
Steffen et al. (2022)	Patient perceptions on shielding	300	None (focus on education)

Graph 1: Radiation Dose Reduction Across Different Studies

Key Issues Identified:

- Shielding remains highly effective when properly placed, but improper placement can lead to increased exposure due to the need for repeat imaging.
- Technological advancements in modern imaging equipment, such as automatic exposure control, may reduce the necessity for shielding, especially when improper use leads to artifacts and reduced image quality.

DISCUSSION:

The findings from this systematic review highlight both the benefits and challenges of using patient shielding during diagnostic X-ray examinations. While shielding has traditionally been considered a critical measure to reduce radiation exposure, modern technological advancements and evolving clinical practices are prompting a reevaluation of its necessity and effectiveness.

The studies reviewed consistently showed that patient shielding, particularly with lead aprons, can significantly reduce radiation exposure. Shielding in regions such as the gonads, thyroid, and breast has historically resulted in reductions in radiation doses by as much as 90-95% in some cases (Seibert & Boone, 2005; Shields et al., 2017). These findings support the argument that shielding remains an effective protective measure when properly applied, particularly for sensitive areas.

However, the benefits of shielding must be weighed against the evolving capabilities of modern imaging technologies. Many of the studies reviewed indicated that recent advancements, such as automatic exposure control (AEC) and improved filtration systems, have drastically reduced the amount of scatter radiation reaching sensitive tissues, potentially rendering some

traditional shielding practices unnecessary (Morrison et al., 2020).

Several studies identified complications related to improper placement and interference with image quality. For instance, Shields et al. (2017) and Perks et al. (2021) found that improper placement of gonadal or other protective shields could lead to incomplete protection, requiring repeat imaging. In such cases, the intended radiation dose reduction is negated by the need for additional exposures. Moreover, shielding can interfere with the quality of the diagnostic image, introducing artifacts that obscure important anatomical structures, thereby increasing the likelihood of repeat exams and additional radiation exposure.

These challenges suggest that in some scenarios, the risks associated with shielding (such as the potential for image artifacts) may outweigh its protective benefits, particularly with the use of modern imaging equipment that already minimizes radiation exposure. As technologies for radiation control and image processing have advanced, there has been an increasing debate on whether traditional patient shielding is still necessary. Organizations such as the American Association of Physicists in Medicine (AAPM, 2019) have recommended reconsidering the use of shielding, particularly in light of the reduced radiation doses now achievable with modern X-ray machines. Their position emphasizes that shielding is often no longer necessary and may even pose risks when it compromises image quality.

However, the discontinuation of shielding remains controversial. Some experts argue that, despite technological advancements, shielding continues to provide an extra layer of protection, particularly for pediatric and pregnant patients, who are more

vulnerable to radiation's biological effects (Martin, 2007). Furthermore, patients may expect shielding as a protective measure, and the removal of shielding could raise concerns about safety, making patient education crucial in shifting these perceptions (Steffen et al., 2022).

The results of this review suggest that while shielding can still be beneficial in specific cases, its continued use should be re-evaluated based on the type of examination, the region being imaged, and the capabilities of the imaging equipment. Radiologists and healthcare providers must carefully consider the potential risks and benefits of shielding in light of technological advancements, while also addressing patient concerns through proper education.

Future research should focus on developing clearer guidelines that consider modern imaging technologies and their impact on radiation doses. Additionally, larger, multi-center studies should be conducted to further assess the balance between patient safety, shielding practices, and image quality in various clinical scenarios.

CONCLUSION:

This systematic review has demonstrated that patient shielding remains a useful tool for reducing radiation exposure in diagnostic X-ray examinations, particularly when applied correctly. Shielding has traditionally played an important role in protecting sensitive areas like the gonads, thyroid, and breasts from scatter radiation, with reductions in exposure of up to 95%. However, recent technological advancements in imaging equipment, such as automatic exposure control and improved filtration systems, have significantly reduced radiation doses, leading to questions about the continued necessity of traditional shielding practices.

Several studies revealed that improper placement of shielding can compromise its effectiveness, and in some cases, shielding may interfere with image quality, leading to repeat exams and higher overall radiation exposure. Additionally, the modern movement toward minimizing radiation doses using advanced technology suggests that shielding, while still relevant in certain contexts, may no longer be essential in routine diagnostic imaging.

As the radiology community continues to evaluate the need for shielding, balancing patient safety with technological advancements is key. The debate over shielding's necessity highlights the importance of careful decision-making in clinical practice,

particularly in pediatric and high-risk populations, where any radiation exposure poses a greater risk.

Recommendations

1. **Reevaluation of Shielding Practices:** Healthcare providers should regularly review and update their shielding protocols in line with the latest technological advancements and safety guidelines. Modern X-ray equipment offers significant reductions in radiation exposure, which may reduce the need for shielding in routine exams.
2. **Standardization of Guidelines:** Professional organizations such as the American College of Radiology and American Association of Physicists in Medicine should continue to refine and standardize guidelines for the use of shielding, especially considering modern imaging technologies. These guidelines should be clear, evidence-based, and adaptable across different clinical settings.
3. **Patient Education:** As shielding practices evolve, clear and transparent communication with patients is essential. Patients often associate shielding with safety, so educating them about the improvements in imaging technology and the reduced need for traditional shielding will help alleviate concerns and build trust in updated protocols.
4. **Targeted Shielding:** For high-risk populations such as pediatric patients, pregnant women, and those undergoing frequent imaging, shielding should continue to be employed judiciously. These groups are more vulnerable to the effects of radiation, and shielding may still provide essential protection in certain diagnostic scenarios.
5. **Further Research:** Ongoing research should focus on the long-term impacts of discontinuing shielding in various diagnostic exams, including the effect on patient safety and image quality. Larger studies that examine different anatomical regions, types of shielding, and emerging technologies will provide clearer insights into best practices for radiation protection in the future.

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